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VITAMIN C ECONOMY IN THE HUMAN SUBJECT¹

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The object of this study was to ascertain (1) the minimal daily requirement of ascorbic acid necessary to protect against scurvy, and (2) the period of protection afforded by saturation with the vitamin.

There is considerable disagreement among the various authors in the field of nutrition as to the amount of vitamin C man requires to maintain health. A high intake of the vitamin is advised by those who use the saturation test based on urinary excretion as the index of ascorbic acid economy, while those who believe a lower intake to be adequate generally base their recommendation upon blood tissue values supported by clinical observations. The entire subject has been recently reviewed (1). It is the purpose of this inquiry to evaluate, as briefly as possible, these two views and to supply additional data which may help to clarify misunderstandings.

To understand the problem of vitamin C economy, it is well to keep in mind two fundamental considerations, which are:

(1) That the only known anatomic lesion of vitamin C deficiency is the scorbutic process (2, 3, 4). Therefore, ascorbic acid, whether synthetic or derived from food, serves but two known purposes, the prevention of scurvy and the treatment for scurvy. (It is possible that vitamin C is active in promoting the intermediary metabolism of aromatic amino acids in premature infants (5) and other animals (6), but unequivocal evidence for this function is lacking.)

(2) That the evaluation of ascorbic acid deficiency in any given individual from an assay of his diet is untrustworthy. Not until a diet can be demonstrated to produce a steady linear decline in the vitamin C content of the white cell-platelet layer (or some index derived from

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whole blood), or to produce scurvy, can one call it deficient. The ability to maintain a fixed plasma level of vitamin C, no matter how small, indicates, for that individual a positive ascorbic acid balance.

The problem, then, is to ascertain how much ascorbic acid is needed to prevent scurvy and how much is required for reserves on an average basis. The amounts required by normal individuals vary somewhat and such variations cannot be explained purely on the basis of surface area. The subject of collagen and reticulum defect in scurvy has been reviewed elsewhere (1, 7, 8).

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A separate study, previously abstracted (1), was conducted on an individual who, following saturation, consumed no ascorbic acid until such time as his plasma vitamin value was zero and the white cell-platelet layer began to decrease. He then received small amounts of the vitamin from biological sources. At first the diet consisted of rice, certain cheeses, eggs, bran, and synthetic vitamins with the exception of vitamin C. The foods used in the experiment were assayed by the method of Bessey (9). After seventy days on the vitamin C free diet, the subject was given 5 mg. of the vitamin as present in orange juice. The white cell-platelet layer vitamin value continued to drop. At the end of fifty days, the vitamin intake was increased to 10 mg. daily and this was accompanied by a slight continued decrease in the blood tissue values. This continued for eighty days when the intake was increased to 18-25 mg. daily which resulted in an initial increase and a subsequent maintenance of the blood tissue levels which lasted from the seventh to the twenty-second month (fig. 1). At no time during the entire twenty-two months did the subject experience any objective or subjective clinical symptoms.

During the twenty-first month an experimental incision, 4 cm. long and 1 cm. deep, was made in the left subscapular area. It was closed with five interrupted sutures. No infection occurred and the wound healed with good tensile strength in six days. The sutures were then removed and a biopsy performed (figs. 2 and 3). In contrast with other studies (13), there appeared to be sufficient collagen and reticulum formation and there was no evidence of weak areas in the tissue structure. Thus it would appear that a diet containing 25 mg. of vitamin C daily

(fig. 4) or possibly less, was sufficient to protect against scurvy and insure wound healing.

Six subjects, volunteers, were placed under hospital conditions.² Their tissues were first saturated by large intakes of ascorbic acid. They were then placed on a diet of eggs, crackers, well cooked meat (free of vitamin C), rice, macaroni, certain cheeses, debittered yeast

FIG. 1. DETERMINATION OF APPROXIMATE MINIMAL VITAMIN C INTAKE REQUIRED TO MAINTAIN FIXED WBC-PLATELET ASCORBIC ACID LEVELS

Plasma and white cell-platelet vitamin C values in a 35 year old male whose dietary intake of the vitamin did not exceed 25 mg. daily for a period of twenty-two months.

and an adequate intake of all vitamins (in preparations) with the exception of ascorbic acid. Tea, coffee, and sugar were allowed. A variety of dishes were prepared from the above by adding numerous seasoning adjuvants. Every five days vitamin C assays were made (10, 11) on blood tissues and plasma of subjects after a twelve hour fast.

² Carried out in part by the U. S. Indian Service Nutrition Laboratory, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, New Mexico.

FIG. 2

FIG. 2. (LEFT) BIOPSY SPECIMEN, LOW POWER MAGNIFICATION OF HEALED WOUND INCURRED AFTER TWENTY-ONE MONTHS OF A DIET, THE VITAMIN C CONTENT OF WHICH DID NOT EXCEED 25 MG. DAILY

FIG. 3

The section shows complete healing by first intention

FIG. 3. (RIGHT) SAME AS FIGURE 2, HIGH MAGNIFICATION

Note abundant newly formed fibroblasts with extensive collagen between them

CASE HISTORIES

(1) J. K. (aged 26, male) weighing 142 pounds was admitted to the hospital with the complaint of muscle pain in the region of the middle third of his

FIG. 4. VITAMIN C ECONOMY IN NORMAL SUBJECTS

Chart showing schematic representation of various vitamin C intakes and laboratory findings. Since no striking laboratory or pathological changes occur between the so-called needless excess and the protective minimum, no absolute figure can be given as a recommended allowance. Any intake on a daily basis within this range appears to be reasonable.

right femur. His antecedent history revealed a compound comminuted fracture of the femur which occurred two years before his present admission. The subject was of a child-like disposition who behaved well but had a great fear of a recurrence of the fracture. He was admitted for physical therapy, reassurance and observation. His past history was unrelated to the present injury

and was essentially non-contributory. The dietary background was fairly good except for an occasional bout of acute alcoholism. The physical examination revealed a well developed male in no apparent physical distress, and revealed no abnormalities whatsoever. The roentgenogram showed excellent union of the fractured shafts of the femur. Objective physical and laboratory measurements were: pulse rate 82, blood pressure 118/84 mm. Hg, hemoglobin 14.4 gm., erythrocytes 4,000,000/cu. mm., white blood cells 6,200/cu. mm. Ascorbic acid study on admission: plasma 0.3 mg./100 ml., white blood cell-platelet value 28 mg./100 gm. A diagnosis of anxiety neurosis was made. He was given 300 mg. of ascorbic acid orally daily for five days at the end of which time more than 75 per cent of his intake was excreted in the urine over a period of twenty-four hours. It was then considered that his tissues were saturated with vitamin C and he was placed on the ascorbic acid-free diet.

(2) M. W. (aged 42, male) weighing 190 pounds was admitted to the hospital with treated trachoma but with persistent blindness due to a well cicatrized macroscopic pannus. His past history is non-contributory except for an appendectomy performed eight years previous to admission. Since he was to be kept in the hospital for ophthalmologic observations and since he didn't particularly want to leave he willingly volunteered for these studies. The physical examination was essentially non-contributory other than the presence of an old trachomatous ophthalmia with a heavy macroscopic pannus. Objective physical and laboratory measurements were: pulse rate 68, blood pressure 108/88 mm. Hg, hemoglobin 15.2 gm., erythrocytes 4,510,000/cu. mm., white cells 7,800/cu. mm. Ascorbic acid: plasma 0.6 mg./100 ml., white blood cell-platelet value 29 mg./100 gm. This subject then received 300 mg. of ascorbic acid daily, on the sixth day he eliminated through the twenty-four hour urine 84 per cent of his ascorbic acid intake. It was considered that his tissues were saturated with ascorbic acid and he was placed on the vitamin C free diet.

(3) T. L. (aged 28, male) weighing 205 pounds was admitted to the hospital with a painful Dupuytren's contracture of the palmar fascia of the right hand. This was the result of local injury and infection seven years prior to the present admission. He was admitted for physical therapy and possible surgical intervention. The past history was non-contributory. The physical examination was not remarkable except for the finding of the contracture and the presence of external hemorrhoids. Objective physical and laboratory measurements were: pulse rate 80, blood pressure 120/80 mm. Hg, hemoglobin 15.4 gm., erythrocytes 4,630,000/cu. mm., white blood cells 7,220/cu. mm. Ascorbic acid: plasma 0.52 mg./100 ml., white blood cell-platelet value 39 mg./100 gm. He was placed on 400 mg. of ascorbic acid orally in divided doses daily for five days at the end of which time 90 per cent of the acid ingested was excreted during twenty-four hours in the urine. He was then placed on the vitamin C free diet.

(4) C. L. (aged 64, male) weighing 210 pounds was admitted to the hospital because of bronchiectasis and ureteral stricture. No reliable history could be obtained that would indicate the possibility of other systemic disease. The subject

was rather anxious to remain in the hospital and enthusiastically volunteered for the observations. He had apparently had symptoms of bronchiectasis for fifteen years; the ureteral stricture had been causing inconvenience for two years. The patient complained occasionally of early morning headache. The subject was a well developed male whose physical findings were dependent on the two entities mentioned along with hypertension (arteriosclerotic-cardiovascular syndrome). Objective physical and laboratory findings were: Emphysematous chest with numerous coarse rhonchi at both bases and a cough productive of thick semipurulent sputum, the heart sounds were forceful in character and regular, retina showed considerable A-V nicking but no hemorrhages; pulse rate 74, blood pressure 164/92 mm. Hg hemoglobin 12.8 gm., erythrocytes 3,810,000/cu. mm., white blood cells 9,400/cu. mm., urine had a persistent trace of albumin with many pus cells but no casts, plasma ascorbic acid was 0.24 mg./100 ml. plasma, and the white blood cell-platelet content was 25 mg./100 gm. He was given 400 mg. of ascorbic acid daily in divided doses and on the fourth day excreted 80 per cent of his vitamin intake. He was then placed on the vitamin C free diet.

(5) A. M. (aged 26, female) weighing 138 pounds was receiving antiluetic treatment for primary syphilis. She was anxious to remain in the hospital since her domestic life was far from satisfactory and willingly volunteered for the observations. Her present illness dated to six months before admission and was discovered through serological and precipitation-flocculation tests. The past history was irrelevant to the present study, except for one small vulvar condyloma there were no remarkable findings on physical examination. Objective physical and laboratory findings were: pulse rate 80, blood pressure 106/72 mm. Hg, hemoglobin 14.6 gm., erythrocytes 4,450,000/cu. mm., white blood cells 5,800/cu. mm., ascorbic acid in plasma 0.22 mg./100 gm. She was given 400 mg. of ascorbic acid daily and on the fifth day excreted 87 per cent of the ingested vitamin. She was then placed on the vitamin C free regime. The subject continued on her diet for one hundred and forty-nine days without any stigmata of scurvy and desired to leave at that time. She was then re-saturated with vitamin C and discharged from the hospital.

(6) C. A. (aged 26, female) weighing 118 pounds was admitted to the hospital for study and physical therapy for post traumatic peripheral pain due to malunion of the lower third of the tibia, and myositis. This illness was dependent on an accident received one year prior to her admission, the fracture having been treated by inexperienced friends. The patient expressed a willingness to remain in the hospital; she was an intelligent person who fully understood the nature of the study and volunteered as a subject. Her past history was non-contributory. The objective physical and laboratory findings were: blood pressure 112/72 mm. Hg, hemoglobin 14.4 gm., erythrocytes 4,420,000/cu. mm., white blood cells 6,200/cu. mm., plasma ascorbic acid 0.57 mg./100 ml., white blood cell-platelet value 24 mg./100 gm. The subject received 350 mg. ascorbic acid daily, in divided doses, for five days, at which time she excreted 77 per cent of the vitamin in the urine. She was then placed on the vitamin C free regime.

Petechial and perifollicular hemorrhages occurred in all subjects, except No. 5, at the end of about 5 months and all were given large doses of vitamin C and a highly nutritious diet. Recovery occurred in seven to ten days.

RESULTS

The results obtained in the study of the six subjects on a vitamin C free diet following saturation showed there were no clinical findings, either subjective or objective, until two weeks previous to the physical signs of scurvy. The findings noted during this period were easy fatigue, lassitude, and irritability. The degree of these symptoms varied with the individual. Shortly thereafter, scurvy set in and the above mentioned symptoms became more severe. The first physical findings noted were petechial and perifollicular hemorrhages; in one case there were tender swollen gums that bled easily. It was felt that these results demonstrated that a period of from five to six months was required to deplete the individual following saturation; the first four months can be considered a period of protection (table 1). It can be deduced that if saturation should take place every four months it would offer protection against scurvy. This would require approximately 2 gm. of the vitamin in divided doses during the period of saturation or represent approximately 8,000 mg. per annum, the equivalent of about 22 mg. per day, a figure very near to that found to be the minimum protective daily dose. Obviously these comparisons cannot be precise but they are suggestive and close enough to warrant such consideration. Our findings further indicate the value of the blood tissue content to be a reliable index of the ascorbic acid status (12, 13). The fact that gingivitis failed to make its appearance except in one case would militate against the view that gingivitis is an early symptom of scurvy.

DISCUSSION

The problem of gum lesions and scurvy is one that has received considerable attention and deserves comment. Recently in a separate study (1) the subject has been reviewed. The added information gained indicates the need for further study but it is highly questionable as to whether the gingival lesion is a scorbutic one on the basis of saturation tests and plasma levels (14). According to Hess (2) absolute

TABLE 1
*Certain Findings Related to Scurvy and Gingivitis in 6 Adult Subjects on a Scorbatic Regime**

NAME	J. E., MALE—26	M. W., MALE—42	T. L., MALE—28	C. L., MALE—64	A. W., FEMALE—26	C. A., FEMALE—26
Initial values						
Ascorbic acid mg./100 ml. plasma.....	1.1	0.96	1.0	1.2	0.96	0.96
Gums.....	30.0 negative	32.0 negative	32.0 negative	28.0 negative	30.0 negative	26.0 negative
Scorbatic findings.....	none	none	none	none	none	none
2 Months						
Ascorbic acid mg./100 ml. plasma.....	0.2	none	none	0.1	none	none
Gums.....	20.0 negative	18.0 negative	18.0 negative	22.0 negative	20.0 negative	16.0 negative
Scorbatic findings.....	none	none	none	none	none	none
4 Months						
Ascorbic acid mg./100 ml. plasma.....	none	none	none	none	none	none
Gums.....	11.0 negative	6.0 ?	8.0 negative	10.0 soreness	10.0 negative	7.0 negative
Scorbatic findings.....	none	none	none	none	none	none
5-6 Months						
Ascorbic acid mg./100 ml. plasma.....	none	none	none	none	none	none
Gums.....	trace	none	trace	none	4	none
Scorbatic findings.....	negative	swollen tender bleed	negative	negative	negative	negative
Scorbatic findings.....	present	present	present	present	present	present

* Teeth were carefully brushed, using fine grade castile soap, morning and night.

† Platelet white cell values.

reliance must not be placed on gum changes for an early diagnosis of the disease. Certain dental changes were noted by Crandon (13) during self induced scurvy, but gum lesions failed to appear. Once they appear it is likely that pyorrhea may set in and the damage will be slow to heal; the pyorrhea may become difficult to treat locally. This may take place in spite of remission of the systemic disease. Local therapy thus assumes the prominent role in gingival disease (14).

In regard to saturation with vitamin C it is interesting to note as Crandon did (13) that a fairly long period of protection exists even though the diet may be entirely lacking in the vitamin. Reports from cruises during the fifteenth century indicate that various members of the crew came down with scurvy at different intervals, some not at all. What they ate in the way of high vitamin C foods on land prior to their sailing probably explains the various degrees of protection among these sailors. There appears to be no need to maintain saturation of the vitamin with needless urinary spill if a small constant daily intake is maintained. On the other hand *saturation with the vitamin may be indicated prior to long trips into territories or conditions where the vitamin supply is questionable or limited*. There appears to be no reason for increased intakes nor a disturbance of ascorbic acid metabolism due to high altitude anoxia (15).

In this report the daily minimum requirement of the normal human subject for a period of twenty-one months has been determined. Since Crandon (13) has shown that a steady decrease in the white cell-platelet ascorbic acid content eventually leads to scurvy, the minimum daily intake must be that which maintains a constant level of these tissues. This has been found to be in the neighborhood of an intake of approximately 20 mg. of vitamin C daily. It seems only reasonable then to assume that safe dietary allowances lie somewhere between the protective minimum and the saturation level (fig. 4). Bessey and White (16) have shown in their data that fixed plasma levels of the vitamin occurred somewhere between 20 mg. and 75 mg. intake of ascorbic acid a day. The scattering of points is probably due to the fluctuation ordinarily encountered in the plasma vitamin content of individuals. Considerable variation occurs in plasma vitamin content in those whose intakes are in the lower brackets of vitamin consumption and plasma indices are apparently not adequate in determining the progress of depletion towards scurvy. The plasma values merely indicate, so

far, degrees of positive economy (1). Such a scatter can be observed in the data of Dodds and McLeod (17) where many plasma values are extremely low and in some cases even zero, and scurvy apparently was not observed.

SUMMARY

1. One subject was placed on a vitamin C free regime until there was a steady linear decline of the blood white cell-platelet values. He was then given at protracted intervals small amounts of the vitamin until such time as the blood tissue white cell-platelet values remained constant (25-26 mg./100 gm.). At the end of twenty-one months on the constantly maintained low values there were no scorbutic manifestations. An experimental wound produced in the twenty-first month was followed by adequate collagen and reticulum formation with normal tissue healing as noted on biopsy.

2. Six subjects were saturated with ascorbic acid (400-500 mg. daily from 4-6 days) and then placed on a diet lacking in vitamin C but normal in all other respects. None of the subjects developed scurvy until five to six months had elapsed and they seemed normal in every respect until two weeks prior to the onset of the disease. Gingivitis appeared only in one case following the advent of perifollicular hemorrhages.

CONCLUSIONS

1. It would appear that an adequate intake of vitamin C should be between the protective minimum (18-25 mg. daily) and the amount required to maintain saturation as represented by excretion in the urine (80-100 mg. daily). The precise intake between the minimal protective dose and the saturation dose is, in the absence of clinical evidence, largely a matter of conjecture.

2. On a vitamin C free diet, a period of protection against scurvy as long as five to six months exists if the subject has been initially saturated with ascorbic acid.

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Since this article has gone to press we have received the August 19th issue of the British Medical Journal. In it there are two communications dealing with Vitamin C. One of them (McMillan, R. B. and Inglis, J. C.) reports a series of 53 cases of frank clinical scurvy. There were only 8 patients with gingivitis and these

were among the most diseased. The other paper (Stamm, W. P., Macrae, T. F. and Yudkin, S.) reveals that 2,962 R.A.F. personnel did not develop scurvy on a diet of 16.8-25.8 mg. of ascorbic acid daily and that the incidence of bleeding gums (19.5 per cent) showed no greater improvement with ascorbic acid than with dummy control tablets. These data appear to corroborate our findings.

M. P.

E. L. L.

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